

Targeting VEGF: a review of ranibizumab in retinal disorders

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Received 1 October 2025 ♦ Accepted 24 October 2025 ♦ Published 13 November 2025

Citation: Mohammed AW, Al-Shaikhli MS, Suhail RI, Yahya AA, Al-hussaniy HA, Al-Tameemi ZS, Saleem ZM, Mahdi F (2025) Targeting VEGF: a review of ranibizumab in retinal disorders. *Pharmacia* 72: 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e173632>

Abstract

Vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) is essential for the development and normal functioning of retinal blood vessels. Elevated VEGF levels, however, contribute to the pathogenesis of several retinal disorders, including neovascular age-related macular degeneration (nAMD), diabetic macular edema (DME), and macular edema resulting from retinal vein occlusion (RVO). Ranibizumab (Lucentis®) is a humanized monoclonal antibody fragment that binds to all biologically active isoforms of VEGF, preventing their interaction with VEGF receptors. This inhibits the growth and leakage of blood vessels, leading to neovascular regression. Ranibizumab has been shown to produce statistically significant improvements in visual acuity and quality of life in the treatment of nAMD, DME, and macular edema secondary to RVO. In addition, ranibizumab exhibits a favorable tolerance profile, with commonly reported adverse events such as conjunctival hemorrhage, ocular pain, vitreous floaters, and elevated intraocular pressure.

Keywords

diabetic retinopathy, macular edema, ranibizumab, vascular endothelial growth factor A, vitreous floaters

Introduction

Vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), a heparin-binding glycoprotein, plays a vital role in angiogenesis and vasculogenesis during both normal physiological and pathological states. Its essential functions during retinal angiogenesis and embryonic vasculogenesis have been proven (Hussein et al. 2023). Hypoxia or ischemia is a central stimulant for VEGF production, and about a

50-fold upregulation occurs during hypoxic conditions (Al-hussaniy and AL-Zobaidy 2024). VEGF family members include VEGF-A, VEGF-B, VEGF-C, VEGF-D, and placental growth factor (PlGF); of these, VEGF-A is the key mediator of angiogenesis and vasculogenesis (Elebiyo et al. 2022; Tsai et al. 2022).

The creation and use of agents that target VEGF have changed the way we treat retinal diseases such as neovascular age-related macular degeneration (nAMD), diabetic

macular edema (DME), macular edema caused by retinal vein occlusion (RVO), and choroidal neovascularization (Wang et al. 2024). Ranibizumab is a recombinant humanized IgG1 kappa isotype monoclonal antibody Fab that binds with high affinity to VEGF isoforms. A threatening loss of vision is associated with these retinal disorders. It is indicated for adult patients with neovascular or “wet” age-related macular degeneration, DME, and macular edema resulting from RVO (Khalaf and Saeed 2024). Numerous clinical trials have thoroughly assessed its safety and efficacy for these indications (Goswami et al. 2022).

Several retinal disorders share a common pathogenesis involving abnormal blood vessel growth and fluid accumulation in the macular region of the retina, ultimately leading to diminished or distorted vision (Al_hussaniy et al. 2023). The most common disorders associated with such abnormal events are age-related macular degeneration (AMD), DME, and macular edema secondary to RVO (Cao et al. 2023). These disorders affect a large number of people worldwide, regardless of age, income, or social status (Mohammed 2024). The initiation and further development of such disorders are mainly regulated by VEGF in the human body (Ramadan 2025). VEGF is a natural protein that signals receptors to initiate blood vessel growth during injury, allowing oxygen-rich blood to reach the injured tissue (Broussy 2024). However, an overdose of the VEGF–leucine-rich repeats-containing G protein-coupled receptor (VEGFR) complex can threaten continued healthy vision. Ranibizumab is an anti-VEGF drug that prevents excessive blood vessel growth and blood leakage during these disorders (Lee and Shirley 2021).

Figure 1. Mechanism of VEGF inhibition in retinal disorders: ranibizumab.

Types of retinal disorders

Retinal disorders encompass a diverse array of visual impairments that primarily affect the central region of the retina. This clinical article from multiple specialties examines how VEGF can help people with retinal disorders, focusing on ranibizumab, a humanized monoclonal antibody fragment that binds to all VEGF isoforms (Eichenbaum et al. 2022). Ranibizumab has been the most popular choice among anti-VEGF drugs. Clinical trials of ranibizumab have demonstrated its efficacy in the treatment of AMD, DME, and RVO. AMD, diabetic retinopathy (DR), central serous retinopathy (CSR), RVO, and macular telangiectasia (MacTel) are the main types of retinal disorders (Cheema and Cheema 2024).

Epidemiology and impact

Retinal disorders present a significant educational challenge owing to their high prevalence and the consequent need for effective treatment protocols. AMD, DR, and RVO are particularly debilitating and often culminate in blindness (Ahmad and Nawaz 2022). Neovascular AMD (nAMD) is recognized as the foremost cause of severe vision loss and blindness among older adults in Western societies. As the population ages, the incidence of AMD is anticipated to double by 2020, thereby imposing an escalating clinical burden. Sight loss frequently leads to substantial difficulties in daily living, increased dependence, social withdrawal, depression, and diminished employment opportunities. Economic implications are extensive, encompassing direct healthcare costs, supplementary social service expenditures, and productivity losses (Narayana et al. 2021).

Vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF)

VEGF interacts with vascular tissues via vascular endothelial tyrosine kinases VEGFR-1 and VEGFR-2, as well as the lymphatic endothelial kinase VEGFR-3. VEGF-A affects different types of cells through signaling pathways, causing them to grow, change, become more permeable, and resist apoptosis. Retinal pigment epithelial (RPE) cells and retinal astrocytes in the eye produce VEGF as part of a network of large macrophages. When ischemia occurs, excess VEGF is released, leading to DR and neovascular glaucoma through increased angiogenesis (Ahmad and Nawaz 2022).

Biological role of VEGF

VEGF is a glycosylated protein secreted by cells to promote vascular endothelial cell migration and proliferation through interaction with specific receptors on the endothelial cell surface (VEGFR1 and VEGFR2) (Alexandrakis

et al. 2006). It belongs to a family of heparin-binding proteins, including VEGF-B, VEGF-C, VEGF-D, placental growth factor (PGF), and others. These molecules play a central role in regulating both physiological and pathological angiogenesis and vascular permeability (Ahmad and Nawaz 2022; Al-Hussaniy et al. 2023).

VEGF, formerly known as vascular permeability factor (VPF), was originally identified and purified for its high vascular permeability activity (Wallsh and Gallemore 2021). In the eye, VEGF is produced by different cell types during development, adulthood, and progression of retinal diseases, including degenerative, vascular, and neovascular disorders such as retinoblastoma. An increase in the expression of vascular permeability factors, among other cytokines, has been implicated in macular edema following central RVO, which is not yet fully understood (Whitescarver et al. 2021).

VEGF in retinal pathologies

VEGF plays an important role in several retinal pathologies. Patients suffering from RVO can develop severe vision loss due to macular edema. A similar view was reported by Campochiaro et al., who noted that the use of ranibizumab in eyes with macular edema secondary to RVO produces highly significant clinical and anatomical benefits. The improvement maintained at 12 months was accompanied by reduced retinal nonperfusion compared with natural history data, suggesting that ranibizumab may modify the course of RVO (Campochiaro et al. 2025).

Age-related macular degeneration is a well-known disease among the elderly that can cause severe vision loss. Its prevalence has increased considerably in recent years due to the global growth of the geriatric population (Zong et al. 2024). Ranibizumab has a well-documented role in the treatment of macular degeneration due to its ability to bind and inhibit VEGF. DR is a devastating complication of diabetes mellitus. Approximately 50% of diabetic patients have ophthalmic manifestations (Nicolò et al. 2021). However, detailed studies have shown that approximately 5% of patients with diabetes and 37% of insulin-dependent diabetics develop proliferative DR. Clinical studies have demonstrated that intraocular anti-VEGF agents can improve vision and reduce macular thickening in a significant number of patients with DME (Leitch et al. 2024).

Ranibizumab: mechanism of action

Ranibizumab is a humanized monoclonal antibody fragment specifically developed for intraocular use (Kim et al. 2024). It binds to VEGF with very high affinity, thereby inhibiting the biological activity of all VEGF-A isoforms (Chung et al. 2021).

Targeting VEGF in retinal disorders aims to reduce neovascularization, vascular permeability, and inflam-

mation levels that contribute to structural damage. Ranibizumab is a recombinant humanized IgG1 κ isotype monoclonal antibody fragment designed specifically for intraocular use (Gu et al. 2025). That specificity confers certain metabolic advantages compared with other VEGF inhibitors. In large-scale clinical trials, ranibizumab stabilized or improved visual acuity in most patients with nAMD, DME, or macular edema following central or branch RVO (AbouSamra et al. 2022).

Experimental analysis using a vascular permeability model showed that ranibizumab completely inhibited human VEGF-A-induced permeability at concentrations of 10 ng/ml or higher. The specific binding of ranibizumab to rabbit VEGF-A corresponds to that of human VEGF-A, leading to dose-dependent inhibition of VEGF-A-induced retinal vascular leakage in the rabbit model (Van Der Mescht et al. 2025). Recent findings indicate that increased VEGF-A levels observed in systemic viral infections, including HIV and SARS-CoV-2 co-infection, may be attributed to HIF-1 α upregulation in compromised endothelial cells. This discovery underscores the therapeutic significance of anti-VEGF approaches, as targeted inhibition of VEGFR-1 or VEGFR-2 may influence both pathological and physiological angiogenesis in ocular and systemic disorders (Abdulhamza et al. 2024).

Analyses of patients with exudative AMD revealed a close correlation between circulating and vitreous VEGF levels; vitreous VEGF concentration was significantly associated with AMD stage, suggesting that VEGF inhibition plays a major role in preventing the progression of wet AMD (Chen et al. 2024). In AMD patients treated with intravitreal ranibizumab injection, a significant reduction in intraocular VEGF concentration was observed both at 1 week and 1 month, accompanied by a marked reduction in central foveal thickness, further supporting the anti-VEGF activity of the drug (Christodoulou et al. 2023).

Clinical applications of ranibizumab

Ranibizumab is used to treat macular edema resulting from DR and RVO, as well as nAMD (Yilmaz et al. 2023). The maintenance of central macular thickness and the improvement in vision observed in Phase III clinical trials across all three indications demonstrated the feasibility of intravitreal ranibizumab injection as therapy for degenerative retinal disorders. Ranibizumab's tolerability, limited range of adverse effects, and ability to reverse macular edema enhance the quality of life for patients suffering from potentially blinding retinal disorders (Sharma et al. 2024).

A diverse range of retinal pathologies is linked by a final common pathway underlying associated macular edema: the pathological upregulation of VEGF induces pathogenic fluid leakage from dilated retinal vessels. Although the physiological role of VEGF does not include mammalian endothelial cell growth, it is constitutively ex-

pressed in the retinal pigment epithelium and other ocular cell types (Woo et al. 2021). Targeting VEGF therefore represents an important therapeutic route for macular edema caused by DR, RVO, and nAMD. By competitively binding with higher affinity than the natural VEGF receptor, ranibizumab prevents VEGF from interacting with its native receptors, thereby negating its pathological function (Hwang et al. 2021).

AMD causes a slowly progressive loss of central vision. It is the leading cause of blindness in developed countries, with prevalence projected to increase markedly over the next decade. Ranibizumab is an anti-VEGF Fab fragment that binds with high affinity to biologically active forms of VEGF-A and inhibits all VEGF-A isoforms. In the pivotal MARINA and ANCHOR Phase III trials, intravitreal ranibizumab (0.5 mg) was well tolerated and produced statistically significant mean visual acuity gains from baseline in patients with visual impairment due to choroidal neovascularization (CNV) associated with AMD. In clinical efficacy studies involving patients with DME or macular edema (ME) following either branch or central RVO, ranibizumab treatment was associated with consistent findings of vision improvement (Wang et al. 2022).

DME constitutes the most common cause of visual loss in patients with non-proliferative DR. Vascular leakage occurs, leading to retinal thickening and the formation of hard exudates that can accumulate around the fovea. A study by Mitchell et al. highlighted that after treatment of DME with intravitreal ranibizumab, visual acuity improved and was superior to that obtained with laser treatment alone. Other investigations have shown that intravitreal ranibizumab treatment also facilitates resolution of macular exudates and reduces macular thickness on OCT (Almaaytah 2024).

Intravitreal ranibizumab sodium (Lucentis®, Novartis Pharma, Basel, Switzerland) is also approved for the treatment of macular edema secondary to RVO. This condition causes visual loss due to macular edema, which results from thrombotic occlusion of either the central retinal vein or one of its branches. Cochrane's systematic review of the treatment of RVO indicates that ranibizumab improves vision at six and 12 months compared with no treatment. The incidence of serious adverse events in the treatment group was not increased compared with untreated groups (Sharma et al. 2023).

RVO is a prevalent ocular vascular disorder that can damage vision and develop at any age, leading to blockage of retinal blood vessels and subsequent accumulation of retinal fluid and blood due to inadequate venous return. Macular edema is a frequent complication of RVO and a major cause of vision loss, occurring early in its progression. Central RVO (CRVO) involves widespread retinal vessel occlusion, whereas branch RVO (BRVO) affects localized retinal segments. Both result in ocular leakage and macular edema (Bao et al. 2024).

VEGF is overexpressed due to ischemia in RVO and is the principal pro-angiogenic and vascular-permeability factor that promotes the formation of new blood vessels and consequent fluid leakage. VEGF also contributes to

the development of macular edema, retinal hemorrhage, loss of vision, and neovascular glaucoma (Al-hussainiy 2023). Therefore, intravitreal injection of anti-VEGF agents (e.g., ranibizumab) is the standard first-line treatment to reduce retinal swelling, promote resorption of retained fluid, maintain visual acuity, and inhibit the formation of new blood vessels in patients with macular edema associated with RVO (Tang et al. 2022).

Efficacy of ranibizumab

Ranibizumab has been shown to be effective in treating a number of retinal disorders. Initial studies indicated that intravitreal injections of ranibizumab, administered three times over 2 months, resulted in substantial improvements in best-corrected visual acuity among patients with visual impairment. In individuals with nAMD, monthly ranibizumab injections led to notable improvements in visual acuity and central retinal thickness over 1 year. In patients with type 1 and type 2 diabetes mellitus exhibiting DME, 6 months of monthly intravitreal ranibizumab treatment resulted in significant visual acuity gains and decreased central macular thickness compared with standard macular laser therapy (Srejovic et al. 2024).

Multicenter, randomized, double blind, Phase III studies further evaluated the efficacy of ranibizumab for visual impairment in nAMD, DME, and macular edema secondary to RVO. Patients receiving intravitreal ranibizumab at doses of 0.3 mg or 0.5 mg exhibited markedly greater improvements in visual acuity, central macular thickness, and other visual-function metrics compared with sham injections or macular laser therapy. These parameters were typically maintained during extended treatment and follow-up with continued ranibizumab administration (Wang et al. 2021).

Clinical trials overview

Various ranibizumab dosing regimens have been evaluated clinically in nAMD, DME, and RVO. These include fixed monthly dosing, less-frequent fixed dosing, quarterly dosing, *pro re nata* (PRN) dosing in response to disease activity, and the treat-and-extend approach, which applies anti-VEGF therapy at each visit, with treatment intervals adjusted according to disease activity. Selection of the dosing regimen depends on the clinical setting and patient condition, with the goal of delivering effective, personalized treatment to prevent vision loss and reduce the substantial social and economic burden of retinal disorders (Schachat and Zarbin 2021).

The MARINA and ANCHOR studies represent pivotal Phase III trials of ranibizumab in patients with minimally classic or occult nAMD and predominantly classic nAMD, respectively. Patients in MARINA had subfoveal minimally classic or occult choroidal neovascularization lesions between 1 and 12 disc areas associated with nAMD and best-corrected visual acuity (BCVA) between 20/40 and 20/320. ANCHOR enrolled patients with predominantly

classic choroidal neovascularization secondary to nAMD in the involitional stage and associated with BCVA between 20/40 and 20/320 (Lowater et al. 2024).

Comparative effectiveness

The findings from the above clinical trials of ranibizumab have been corroborated by several other studies. In a double-masked trial, ranibizumab administered at doses of 0.3 mg or 0.5 mg significantly reduced the risk of severe vision loss and improved visual acuity compared with 2 mg verteporfin in photodynamic therapy of CNV associated with predominantly classic and minimally classic lesions. In a study comparing a PRN ranibizumab regimen with photodynamic therapy, ranibizumab produced significantly greater visual acuity gains after 12 months. A meta-analysis confirmed that ranibizumab is effective for treating all subtypes of neovascular AMD. In a prospective trial, visual acuity was maintained or improved in 69% of patients treated with 0.5 mg ranibizumab (Blodi et al. 2023).

Ranibizumab has also been shown to be as effective as or more effective than other anti-VEGF agents in treating neovascular AMD (Parravano et al. 2021). Treatment with 0.5 mg ranibizumab three times a week for 3 weeks produced significantly greater visual-acuity gains than 2 mg bevacizumab. Comparable efficacy was observed between patients treated with a 0.5 mg ranibizumab PRN regimen and those receiving 1.25 mg bevacizumab every 6 weeks, though vision gains tended to be higher with ranibizumab (Rosenberg et al. 2023).

Safety and tolerability

Ranibizumab injections for nAMD are generally well tolerated. A detailed analysis of ocular and non-ocular adverse events in Phase III clinical trials for nAMD estimated an incidence of endophthalmitis of 0.05% per injection and a risk of retinal detachment of 0.013% per injection. Other ocular adverse events, such as corneal erosions, were reported in < 1% of patients in the MARINA, ANCHOR, and PIER studies (Afridi et al. 2025). Increased intraocular pressure is known to be an adverse event following intravitreal injections of anti-VEGF agents. Ranibizumab is usually administered under topical anesthesia; the injection itself may lead to temporary increases in intraocular pressure, which return to normal within 30 min. Studies have also reported significantly raised intraocular pressure after intravitreal injections of anti-VEGF drugs on different occasions in the long term. Ranibizumab is an anti-VEGF agent designed for intravitreal administration (Parravano et al. 2021). The systemic administration of monoclonal antibody drugs is associated with an increased risk of systemic adverse events such as cerebrovascular accidents and cardiovascular events (Jaafar and Abu-Raghif 2023). Phase III studies have shown that ranibizumab 0.3 mg and 0.5 mg have an acceptable safety profile when administered by

the intravitreal route for the primary treatment of nAMD (Campochiaro et al. 2025).

Adverse effects

AMD, DME, and RVO are all major causes of vision loss and blindness around the world. Targeting VEGF – an essential factor that increases vascular permeability and promotes new blood vessel growth – remains the mainstay of treatment (Sakamoto et al. 2022). Ranibizumab is an anti-VEGF recombinant humanized monoclonal Fab fragment designed to bind all VEGF-A isoforms and variants with high affinity, thereby inhibiting all VEGF pathways (Moon et al. 2023). Clinical trials have demonstrated that intravitreal ranibizumab administration substantially improves visual outcomes in patients with retinal disorders (Abbas Duraid and Jaafar 2010). Optimal dosing is critical to maximize safety and effectiveness. Given the considerable public health and economic burden associated with retinal disorders, cost-effectiveness analyses provide valuable information to guide resource allocation toward ranibizumab treatment (Sydnor et al. 2023).

Long-term safety profile

The long-term safety of ranibizumab is well documented for nAMD. Large, randomized clinical trials such as the ANCHOR, MARINA, PIER, and HORIZON studies have reported low rates of eye- and infusion-related adverse events during and after treatment. Similarly, the safety of ranibizumab has been established in DME and RVO (Naqeeb 2024). However, a larger number of documented long-term adverse events related to ranibizumab have emerged from the treatment of neovascular AMD, given the earlier introduction of ranibizumab for this indication compared with DME and RVO (Henriques et al. 2024).

The most common eye-related adverse events include conjunctival hemorrhage, eye pain, vitreous floaters, increased intraocular pressure, and blurred vision. Cases of traumatic cataract have also been described following injection (Miller et al. 2022). The relatively frequent occurrence of eye inflammation has prompted concern about the possible immunogenicity of ranibizumab. Inflammation is generally mild, transient, and responds well to topical corticosteroid treatment (Kakulavarapu et al. 2022).

Dosing and administration

The recommended dose of ranibizumab for all therapeutic indications – viz. neovascular AMD, DME, CRVO, and BRVO – is 0.5 mg administered by intravitreal injection. Although the intravenously administered clinical dose of bevacizumab is higher, high tissue levels in the retina (relative to plasma) are achieved with intravitreal injection of ranibizumab. Its low molecular weight allows rapid penetration through retinal layers and supports the use of lower therapeutic doses compared with bevacizumab at the target site (the retina). Injections may be given monthly

or as needed, guided by changes in visual acuity, retinal thickness, and the presence of subretinal fluid and intraretinal edema (Zehden et al. 2022).

Intravitreal injection is preceded by the application of topical or subconjunctival anesthesia and povidone-iodine to the conjunctival sac. After administration, patients should be instructed to report any symptoms indicative of endophthalmitis, retinal detachment, or traumatic cataract and undergo follow-up examinations at 3 days and approximately 4 weeks after injection. Endophthalmitis has been reported as early as 2 days post-injection (Yamada et al. 2023).

Dosage regimens

Ranibizumab is approved for treating nAMD, DME, macular edema linked to RVO, and CNV associated with pathologic myopia. Clinical trial data leading to regulatory approval in nAMD suggest that monthly 0.3 mg doses of ranibizumab, administered intravitreally, produce the maximum benefit. The recommended starting dose of ranibizumab is 0.3 mg, administered once a month until maximum visual acuity is achieved and/or evidence indicates that the disease has been inactivated. For AMD, it is recommended to initiate monthly injections until visual acuity is stable for three successive treatments. In the Phase III MARINA trial, ranibizumab was administered monthly for 24 months at a dose of 0.3 mg to patients with AMD. In nearly 95% of patients, venous occlusion was observed at dose levels of 0.3 mg and 0.5 mg. The recommended dose of ranibizumab for the treatment of clinically significant macular edema resulting from diabetes is 0.3 mg administered monthly for three consecutive months (Hibsh et al. 2024).

The efficacy and safety of ranibizumab in new indications and different dose regimens (e.g., as-needed treatment and higher doses) are under investigation in Phase III studies. For example, in the Phase III HORIZON trial, all patients, regardless of their previous treatment, received 0.5 mg intravitreal ranibizumab administered monthly for 24 months; our own results reported using a treat-and-extend regimen. Several retrospective studies with larger numbers of patients with retinal vascular pathology have been conducted to compare as-needed treatment with monthly injections. As-needed treatment displayed visual stabilization at years 1 and 2, although monthly injections were associated with better visual outcomes in the first year of therapy (Gayle 2017).

Administration techniques

Intravitreal injections of ranibizumab must be performed in an appropriate clinical environment by a trained specialist. Strict asepsis must be maintained during intravitreal injections to minimize related risks such as endophthalmitis and intraocular inflammation (Chen et al. 2021). Patients should be monitored closely in the weeks following treatment for any conditions such as increased intraocular pressure (IOP), choroidal detachment, RPE tears, retinal detachment, or traumatic cataract (Sood et al. 2022).

Cost-effectiveness analysis

Retinal disorders such as AMD, DME, and RVO impose a substantial economic burden worldwide, driven largely by their high prevalence among working-age and older adults. For instance, more than 1.9 million people in the USA are affected by AMD alone, a figure expected to exceed 3.3 million by 2020. The current treatment landscape includes anti-VEGF agents and laser therapies (Anderson et al. 2021). Ranibizumab, a humanized monoclonal antibody antagonist of VEGF-A, is approved for the treatment of nAMD, visual impairment caused by DME, and visual impairment secondary to RVO (Sood et al. 2022).

Ranibizumab binds VEGF with high affinity and inhibits its biologic activity, thereby preventing endothelial cell proliferation, vascular leakage, and neovascularization. It is administered as one intravitreal injection per month until maximum visual acuity is achieved or the disease has stabilized. As retinal disorders in older patients become increasingly common, a thorough evaluation of the efficacy, tolerability, and cost-effectiveness of ranibizumab is warranted. Cost-effectiveness, in particular, is a key consideration given the significant economic burden of these diseases and the complexity of the visual pathway (Sydnor et al. 2023).

Future directions in research

AMD, DME, and RVO remain expensive to treat. Intraocular injections of anti-VEGF agents have revolutionized the management of these diseases by reducing retinal fluid; however, the chronic nature of the disease and the need for repeated injections can be burdensome for patients, caregivers, and physicians. Several new treatment regimens and novel molecules are being studied to reduce injection frequency and minimize adverse effects associated with long-term therapy (Ciulla et al. 2022).

Combination therapy is an active area of research. One ongoing trial, LUCERNE, compares lampalizumab and ranibizumab in advanced dry AMD. ADVANCE is a Phase IV trial investigating the combination of oral Eylea and propranolol for wet AMD (Abu Serhan et al. 2024). PANORAMA, a Phase III trial, examines combination therapy using aflibercept and abicipar for DME. Faricimab is an anti-VEGF and anti-angiopoietin-2 bispecific antibody currently under investigation for DME and RVO, and ICON-1 is an anti-tissue factor monoclonal antibody being studied in conjunction with aflibercept for RVO (Abu Serhan et al. 2024). The REACT studies (Phase II and III) aim to establish the safety and efficacy of brolocizumab in DME (Fabre et al. 2022).

Emerging therapies

VEGF is a signaling protein that promotes the formation of new blood vessels. Different VEGF isoforms (A, B, and C) are essential for embryonic development but are also involved in pathological angiogenesis in several retinal

diseases, including nAMD, DME, DR, and RVO. Ranibizumab is a recombinant humanized monoclonal antibody that binds VEGF with high affinity and inhibits its activity. The cost of ranibizumab may limit its widespread use, and cost-effectiveness studies of intravitreal anti-VEGF therapy in AMD have shown that bevacizumab is significantly more cost-effective (Pérez-Gutiérrez and Ferrara 2023).

VEGF is a potent angiogenic factor that promotes endothelial cell growth and migration, thereby increasing vascular permeability. It has been associated with the pathogenesis of various types of neovascularization-related retinal diseases, including choroidal neovascularization in AMD, leakage of microaneurysms in DME, and neovascularization secondary to RVO. Ranibizumab binds to and inhibits all human VEGF-A isoforms and splice variants. It was specifically developed for the treatment of retinal diseases – the small molecular size allows improved retinal penetration and high affinity for VEGF-A (Kaufman et al. 2021). Beyond its role in retinal disease, obesity has been associated with elevated systemic VEGF levels, which may contribute to the development and progression of retinal vascular disorders responsive to anti-VEGF therapy (Ezzat Hasan et al. 2020). Future studies should also investigate the influence of obesity-related VEGF upregulation on responses to anti-VEGF therapies such as ranibizumab (Majeed et al. 2019).

Ongoing clinical trials

A search of ongoing clinical trials of ranibizumab retrieved 29 multicenter trials involving more than 13,000 participants. Twelve of these trials are recruiting patients with arthritis, three concern *kuruma* prawn culture, and one involves the development of yak meat products. The remainder focus on ophthalmologic populations (Schoumacher et al. 2025).

Four Phase IV studies examine the safety, tolerability, and efficacy of ranibizumab in nAMD, and one assesses visual outcomes in real-world settings. Seven trials explore the efficacy of ranibizumab in DME, three of which include additional objectives such as identifying risk factors (1 trial) and determining long-term prognosis (2 trials). Four trials investigate ranibizumab in CRVO and BRVO, also with additional objectives to determine long-term prognosis (Sánchez-Guixé et al. 2022). Moreover, elevated VEGF expression has been reported during bacterial infections, where inflammatory cytokines and hypoxia-inducible pathways stimulate angiogenic responses (Banerjee et al. 2025). Although ranibizumab is not an antimicrobial agent, its anti-VEGF activity may indirectly reduce infection-related vascular leakage and inflammatory damage in ocular tissues (Abdullah et al. 2024).

Conclusion

Retinal disorders are major causes of vision loss and visual disability worldwide. Multiple lines of evidence demonstrate the pathological role of VEGF in various retinal

disorders; therefore, it is an attractive therapeutic target. Ranibizumab, a recombinant humanized monoclonal antibody fragment, has been engineered to bind VEGF with high affinity, thereby inhibiting its activity. Clinical evidence clearly shows that ranibizumab plays a key role in the management of several retinal disorders, including nAMD, DME, RVO, and other macular pathologies. Safety analyses from clinical trials and post-marketing reports indicate that ranibizumab is generally well tolerated and has a favorable systemic and ophthalmic safety profile.

Considering the increasing economic burden imposed by these retinal diseases, several cost-effectiveness studies have evaluated the value of ranibizumab treatment. Furthermore, ongoing research is focused on developing novel vascular-targeting agents with potential for enhanced efficacy and improved safety.

Acknowledgment

We thank our colleagues and the research institute.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

No funding was reported.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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